

Appendix 2.3: Detailed list of references used for the assessment of nature’s contributions to people (NCP) in the regional assessment for Europe and Central Asia (ECA)

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2.2. Status and trends of nature's contributions to people in Europe and Central Asia

2.2.1. Status and trends of regulating NCP

2.2.1.3. Regulation of air quality

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2.3. Effects of trends in nature's contributions on quality of life in Europe and Central Asia

2.3.1. Contributions to food-energy-water security

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2.3.4. Environmental equity and justice

2.3.4.2. Intra-generational distributive equity and justice

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2.3.5. Valuing nature's contributions to people

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